

Retrofitting of pre-damaged welds using the spot-heating technique

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Abstract:

Welded steel bridges are prone to fatigue cracking due to increased axle loads of heavy-duty traffic and extended operation times. There are multiple weld toe treatments like grinding, TIG dressing and mechanical impact treatment that can prolong the fatigue life of pre-damaged welds as long as no macroscopic cracks have initiated at the weld toe. However, these methods usually require expensive gear, require skilled operators, are time consuming or the quality control proves to be difficult. Spot-heating is a simple and cheap method for fatigue improvement that has already been investigated in the 50s and 60s, but the application has not been implemented widespread in practice in recent years. The University of Applied Sciences in Munich performed fatigue tests on pre-damaged and subsequently spot-heated specimens that showed a good efficacy of the technique making it a promising approach for retrofitting. In this paper the common post-weld treatment methods and their effectiveness on pre-damaged welded structures as well as the previous results of the experimental investigations using the spot-heating technique are presented.

Keywords: Spot-heating, fatigue, retrofit, existing structures

1 Introduction

Welded steel bridges worldwide have exceeded their calculated service life. In Europe more than two thirds of metallic bridges are older than 50 years [1]. Due to accumulating fatigue damage and increasing axle loads of heavy-duty traffic, the probability of crack initiation and propagation to failure of the structure increases with continued use. Weld toe treatments like grinding, TIG-dressing and high frequency mechanical impact treatment (HFMI) can increase the fatigue strength of constructional details with weld toe failure, see Figure 1. These methods can be considered in the fatigue design of new constructions according to the recommendations of the International Institute of Welding (IIW) [2] and their applicability to pre-damaged components has been proven in studies. However, these methods can be labour-intensive, require expensive gear or skilled operators for execution and quality control. Spot-heating on the other side is a simple and cheap procedure that can increase the fatigue strength immensely. However, for this method only investigations on as-welded components without pre-damage and only 2 different constructional details have been published. The University of Applied Sciences in Munich therefore performed fatigue tests on pre-damaged and subsequently spot-heated components. This paper tries to provide an overview of the conventional weld toe treatments and their efficacy on pre-damaged components and presents the previous results of the own investigations.

Figure 1: suited and unsuited details for weld toe treatment

2 Conventional weld toe treatments

2.1 HFMI

In the HFMI process, a hardened steel pin plastically deforms the weld toe. This leads to an enlargement of the weld toe radius reducing the notch effect of the weld. Furthermore, the surface of the treated area is strain-hardened increasing the fatigue strength of the weld toe region, especially when applied to mild steels. The third effect is the introduction of compressive residual stresses at the treated weld toe increasing the fatigue life through crack closure effects. This effect is dominant in high strength steels. The IIW recommendations [2], [3], the German DAST-guideline 026 [4] and prEN 1993-1-9 [5] enable the consideration of HFMI in the fatigue design of new structures. According to [3] the fatigue strength can be increased by up to 8 FAT-classes, see Figure 2, depending on the yield strength f_y and stress ratio R .

If there are no cracks present, HFMI can also be applied to pre-damaged welds. Multiple studies e.g. [6], [7], [8], [9] show great extensions of fatigue life and that the damage sum can at least be reset to zero after application, also see Figure 10 and [10]. In [11] HFMI is recommended for use on pre-damaged welds.

HFMI is already being used to retrofit existing structures like crane bridges [12] or federal road bridges [13], but without the consideration in the fatigue assessment.

The advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of HFMI to existing structures are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 2: Possible improvement of FAT classes through HFMI for new structures according to [3]

Table 1: Advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of HFMI to existing structures

advantages	disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high efficacy • very high process speed • comparably easy application • large database of fatigue tests on pre-damaged components 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • requires special gear • only applicable to details with weld toe failure • requires cleaning and removing of paint • the peening trace introduces sharp edges, therefore the surface quality P3 acc. to ISO 8501-3 [14] cannot be reached

2.2 TIG dressing

In TIG dressing, the tungsten inert gas welding process is used without weld consumable to remelt the weld toe which results in an enlargement of the weld toe radius and removing of imperfections, see Figure 3, leading to an increase in fatigue strength. The IIW recommendations [2] allow a benefit factor of 1.3 (max. FAT 112) for the fatigue strength in the design of new structures, when TIG dressing is applied. [15] contains recommendations for execution.

Multiple studies have shown that TIG dressing is also effective when applied to pre-damaged structures [10], even for welds with fatigue cracks. By fusing the damaged material in the vicinity of the weld toe, cracks can be effectively removed. However, care must be taken to ensure that there is no crack tip remaining under the remelted material, otherwise rapid crack growth will occur. TIG dressing is recommended for use on pre-damaged welds in [11].

The advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of TIG dressing to existing structures are summarised in Table 2.

Figure 3: Weld seam shapes – left) as-welded, right) after TIG dressing [15]

Table 2: Advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of TIG-dressing to existing structures

advantages	disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high efficacy • large database of fatigue tests on pre-damaged components • remelting of cracks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • slow process speed • only applicable to details with weld toe failure • requires cleaning and removing of paint • requires skilled operator, especially in out-of-position • requires a welding procedure qualification in EXC3 and 4 acc. to EN 1090-2 [16]

2.3 Grinding

Weld toes can be ground using a burr or disc grinder to remove imperfections and enlarge the weld toe radius, see Figure 4, which results in an increase in fatigue strength. The IIW recommendations [2] allow a benefit factor of 1.3 (max. FAT 112) for the fatigue strength in the design of new structures, when burr grinding is applied. [15] contains recommendations for execution. Disc grinders show a comparatively low efficacy [17] and are therefore not recommended by [2].

There are only few studies on pre-damaged welds. In [18] burr grinding was applied to cracked beams with welded cover plates. Even though the cracks were removed by grinding the fatigue life could not be extended significantly. In [8], [19], also see Figure 10, pre-damaged weld seams without macroscopic cracks were ground using a burr and disc grinder. The burr ground specimens showed a great extension of fatigue life. The efficacy of the disc grinder was comparatively low. Burr grinding is more suitable for the in-situ application than disc grinding anyway due to its better accessibility. Both methods are recommended for use on pre-damaged welds in [11].

The advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of burr grinding to existing structures are summarised in Table 3.

Figure 4: Burr grinding of weld toes – left) recommendations according to [15], right) ground weld toe [15]

Table 3: Advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of burr grinding to existing structures

advantages	disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high efficacy when applied to uncracked welds • requires only little surface preparation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • comparatively very slow process speed • only applicable to details with weld toe failure • requires skilled operator • only small database of fatigue tests on pre-damaged components

3 Spot-heating

3.1 Previous research

The positive effects of spot-heating on the fatigue strength of welded components was already investigated in the 1950s and 1960s. Puchner [20], [21] and Gurney [22], [23], [24], [25] performed fatigue tests on specimens with the constructional details longitudinal stiffener and lateral attachment in as-welded and spot-heated condition. Therefore, the specimens were spot-heated up to 650°C for a short period of time. During the cooling phase compressive residual stresses are introduced due to heterogeneous plastic deformation and phase transformation, see Figure 5-a). The resulting residual compressive stresses increase the fatigue strength of the weld toe area, that is often subjected to residual tensile stresses in unannealed condition. The SN-curve in Figure 5-b) shows the results of fatigue tests on lateral attachments. The fatigue strength could be increased by 98% through spot-heating.

Figure 5: a) schematic sketch based on [20], b) SN-curve for lateral attachment - data taken from [26], c) SN-curve for longitudinal stiffener – data taken from [26]

Experimental and theoretical investigations regarding the spot-heat temperature were conducted in [27]. It could be determined that at a temperature of 400 to 500°C residual compressive stresses at 50% of the yield strength could be introduced.

In [28] numerical and experimental investigations on specimens with welded longitudinal stiffeners were performed. At the end of the stiffener 3 paths were heated up to 350°C, see Figure 6. The residual stress state was quantified through a numerical simulation. The numerical model was validated by residual stress measurements using X-ray diffraction. The results of the simulation showed that compressive stresses could be introduced at the weld toe and the residual tensile stresses at the weld root could be significantly reduced, see Figure 6.

Figure 6: left) paths of spot-heating [28], right) results of numerical simulation of residual stresses [28]

In [29] crack growth experiments were performed on thermally stress relieved specimens with a single edge notch (SEN). It could be shown that when the area of the crack was locally heated up to 300°C in loaded state, the crack growth was retarded. This could not be observed when the heat treatment was applied in unloaded state, see Figure 7.

Fig. 3. Crack length versus number of cycles: □ - -, without heat treatments; Δ - -, before and after heat treatment was applied at the unloaded state; \bullet - -, before and after heat treatment was applied at the loaded state.

Figure 7: Results of crack growth experiments [29]

In [30] further crack growth experiments on SEN specimens were performed. A spot with a diameter of 12 mm in the vicinity of the crack tip was heated in unloaded state. The distance between the heat spot and the crack tip varied between -3 and +7 mm (negative values describe positions between crack tip and the notched edge). It could be shown even in unloaded state the crack growth could be retarded when the spot was positioned between crack tip and the unnotched edge. Higher temperatures led to greater retardation of crack growth, see Figure 8.

Figure 8: Crack growth retardation depending on the heat spot temperature [30]

3.2 Experimental investigations at the University of Applied Sciences Munich

To investigate the applicability of spot-heating to pre-damaged structures, specimens with lateral attachments were welded, pre-damaged, spot heated and then tested for fatigue. Due to identical dimensions, material and welding parameters the tests are evaluated together with the results of [8].

3.2.1 Fabrication of specimens

The specimens were made from flat steel with the steel grade S355J2 according to EN 10025-2 [31]. The dimensions are given in Figure 9–a). The welding parameters are summarized in Table 4. After the pre-damage, see chapter 3.2.2, the specimens were spot-heated to yellowish white heat using an acetylene torch, see Figure 9 and quenched with water when the annealing colors indicated a temperature below 500°C. After a minute when the specimens cooled down to 100°C, the next heat spot was introduced.

Figure 9: a) specimen dimensions, b) spot-heating with acetylene torch, c) glowing heat spot

Table 4: Fabrication of specimens - welding parameters

specimen	process acc. to EN ISO 4063	filler material acc. to EN ISO 14341-A	Ø electrode [mm]	shield gas acc. to ISO 14175	I [A]	U [V]	v [mm/s]
lateral attachment	135	G 46 4 M21 4Si1	1.0	M21	190-200	24.5-25.5	6.3

3.2.2 Pre-damaging of specimens

The number of pre-damage load cycles $N_{D=1}$ (damage sum $D = 1.0$) was calculated using Eq.(1). $\Delta\sigma_{C,95\%}$ is the characteristic fatigue strength of the specimens in as-welded state that was determined in [8]. $\Delta\sigma$ is the stress range used in the fatigue test. The pre-damaging was performed using a Sincotec Powerswing 600 high-frequency pulsator. The

load ratio was $R = 0.1$. After the application of the load cycles, the weld toes were checked for cracks using penetration testing. No cracks were found after pre-damaging.

$$N_{D=1} = \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma_{C,95\%}}{\Delta\sigma} \right)^3 * 2 * 10^6 \quad (1)$$

3.2.3 Fatigue tests

The pre-damaged and spot-heated specimens were subsequently tested for fatigue in the same testing rig. A frequency deviation of $\Delta f = -0.1$ Hz was chosen as abort criterion analogous to [8]. The fatigue tests were also performed with the load ratio $R = 0.1$.

All spot-heated specimens were initially tested at a stress range of $\Delta\sigma = 150$ N/mm² and did not fail until $5 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles and thus were declared as run-outs. The loads were then increased to $\Delta\sigma = 200$ N/mm² and all specimen failed in the clamping area.

The results of the fatigue tests are summarized in a SN-curve and a box plot in Figure 10. The box plot shows the experimentally determined damage sums D_{treat} defined as cumulated load cycles ΣN over the pre-damage load cycles $N_{D=1}$. It can be seen that all post weld treatments are still effective, even after pre-damaging. Grinding with a flap disc shows the least effectiveness. Large-area HFMI shows to be more effective than single peening traces. The largest damage sums could be reached using the spot-heating method – up to $D_{treat} = 97.6$.

Figure 10: Results of fatigue tests – left) SN-curve, right) box plot

3.2.4 DIC-measurements

To further investigate the spot-heating method applied to welded lateral attachments, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was performed to quantify the plastic strains after the heating process. Therefore, a stochastic pattern was applied to the surface of a specimen using temperature-stable coating. The specimen was then spot-heated on the backside according to Figure 9-a). The strains were captured using an ARAMIS GOM System with 2 cameras, see Figure 11-a). The final principal plastic strain distribution after the specimen has cooled down to room temperature is given Figure 11-b). It can be seen that positive plastic strains occurred in the vicinity of the weld toe in the range of 0.75 to 0.95% that result in elastic compressive stresses.

3.2.5 Potential of spot-heating in the rehabilitation of existing structures

It could be shown that spot-heating is very effective when used on pre-damaged welds without macroscopic cracks. Due to its easy applicability, no need for expensive gear, high process speed and no need for surface preparation, it appears to be suitable for the in-situ use on existing structures. Furthermore, it could be shown that residual stresses in the vicinity of the weld root could also be lowered. This leads to the assumption that it could also be used on welded details with weld root failure that cannot be retrofitted using common post-weld treatments like HFMI, TIG dressing or grinding.

However, the spot-heating method was only examined on the details lateral attachment and longitudinal stiffener in as-welded condition and there are only a few tests on pre-damaged specimens. The application to transverse welds is to be investigated. Furthermore, the effects on the integrity of the parent material have to be evaluated. In addition, there are no concepts for quality control yet.

The advantages and disadvantages of spot-heating applied to existing structures are summarized in Table 5

a)

b)

Figure 11: DIC-measurements– a) test setup, b) distribution of principle plastic strains at room temperature after spot-heating

Table 5: Advantages and disadvantages of the in-situ application of spot-heating to existing structures

advantages	disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • very high efficacy when applied to uncracked welds • requires no surface preparation • easy and fast process • possibly applicable to details with weld root failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • only 2 constructional details were investigated • only a few fatigue tests on pre-damaged components • effects on the integrity of the parent material must be evaluated • no quality control concept

4 Summary and scope

This article briefly summarizes the efficacy of common weld toe treatments applied to pre-damaged welds and evaluates their suitability when used on existing structures. Previous research on the spot-heating method is summarized and own experiments on pre-damaged specimens retrofitted using spot-heating are presented.

Due to its high efficacy and easy applicability, spot-heating is a promising technique. However, due to the very limited database further investigations regarding the effect on the integrity of the parent material and a concept for quality control have to be performed.

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